

NORMALIZED DIFFERENCE VEGETATION INDEX (NDVI) IN THE FLOWERING PHASE OF SOYBEAN GROWN IN DIFFERENT SOIL CONDITIONS

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IMPROVING CROPS

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INTRODUCTION

This study aimed to examine the influence of different soil types on the NDVI value in the flowering phase of diverse soybean germplasm.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The trial was conducted in 2020 within the experimental plots of the Institute of Field and Vegetable Crops in Rimski Šančevi.

An identical set of over 100 soybean genotypes were grown on two different soil types, sandy and clay.

In flowering, soybean genotypes were photographed using an unmanned aerial vehicle-DJI P4M and a multispectral camera with five spectral channels (Red, Green, Blue, Red Edge, Near-Infrared).

DJI P4M and a multispectral camera

Red and Near-Infrared channels were used to calculate the NDVI and assess the effect of different soil types on soybean genotypes in one of the critical development stages such as flowering.

RESULTS and CONCLUSIONS

The results showed different NDVI values between soybean genotypes grown on sandy and clay soil.

Genotypes sown on low-quality sandy soil in the flowering phase had on average a lower value of NDVI by over 8% compared to the same set of genotypes grown on clay soil.

Graph 1. NDVI values

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